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Artificial Potential Field-Based Kinematic Bidirectional-RRT for Robot-Trailer Kinematics

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Abstract—Autonomous mobile robot systems with trailers are gaining traction in logistics, industrial and construction settings due to their ability to safely transport heavy loads. However, path planning for these systems is challenging due to their complex non-linear dynamics. Existing methods follow a hierarchical approach to navigation, charting an initial global plan and addressing trailer kinematics locally using advanced control techniques. This approach often results in inefficient paths, complicating the task of local controllers. Moreover, integrating all potential robot configurations with kinematic constraints into global planning for large-scale, complex, and unstructured environments escalates computational demands. This paper proposes a novel approach that incorporates kinematic constraints directly into the global planning phase using an Artificial Potential Field-based Kinematic Bidirectional-RRT (APF-based KB-RRT) algorithm specifically adapted for an ackermann robot with a trailer. By addressing these constraints early in the planning process, we aim to improve overall path efficiency. To address the non-linearities in the trailer kinematics, we employ the Newton-Raphson method. Simulation results demonstrate the efficacy of our proposed methodology in generating precise and efficient motion plans, characterized by minimal computational complexity. Concurrently, qualitative findings underscore the robustness of our approach, particularly evident in challenging scenarios, such as initial trailer positions close to folding angles.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous vehicle-trailer path planning is becoming increasingly prevalent in fields, such as logistics [1], mobility [2] and construction sites [3]. These systems offer a promising solution for enhancing the safety during complex maneuvers, typically involving heavy equipment. However, the development of such systems presents a significant challenge due to their non-linear dynamics.

The generation of collision-free paths for autonomous mobile robots has been extensively studied in literature. Typically, these methods follow a hierarchical two-stage approach [4]: a global planning phase, where the objective is to chart a path that avoids known obstacles, followed by a refinement stage which addresses the robot’s kinematic constraints. The refinement includes either a path-smoothing step applied to the whole path [5] [6] [7], or a local planner [8] [9] which computes a feasible path towards local goal points, which are

part of the initial global path. The global planner is responsible for roughly directing the robot to reach consecutive higher-level mission goals, while the local planner is responsible for keeping the robot safe, through the generation of a finer-scale, short-term motion plan.

Especially when dealing with non-holonomic robots, such as robots with trailers, the two-stage approach for path planning can be inefficient. This arises from the fact that kinematic constraints are not considered during the global path generation step. As a result, the planned trajectories may be unfeasible to follow without violating the robot’s kinematics capabilities. This can lead to significant deviations from the predefined route and goal pose, compromising mission success and potentially posing safety risks. Integrating kinematic knowledge directly into global planning can greatly enhance navigation performance, especially for robots with trailers. However, representing all possible robot configurations with kinematic constraints for large-scale, complex and unstructured environments can lead to increased computational complexity.

In this paper, we built-upon an APF-based KB-RRT algorithm [10], specifically built for cluttered and unstructured environments, adapted accordingly to facilitate an ackermann robot attached with a trailer. To the best of our knowledge, this work is the first that adapts the KB-RRT algorithm to a robot-trailer configuration. The main contribution of our approach is the incorporation of the robot-trailer kinematic equations to guide the expansion of the RRT and more specifically the utilization of Newton-Raphson method to solve the non-linear system by inverting the robot-trailer kinematic equations. Simulation results verify that our proposed methodology can provide accurate results in a short computational time and handle various initial and final positions configurations.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews the state-of-the-art for tractor-trailer and kinematically-constrained path planning. Section III provides a detailed description of our proposed methodology, while Section IV presents the simulation results. Finally, Section V summarizes the paper.

II. RELATIVE WORK

Recent studies have focused on directly addressing the kinematic constraints within the global planner, eliminating the need for a separate refinement process. In that direction, graph search-based [11], incremental sampling-based [12], optimization-based [13] and learning-based [14] planners have been proposed.

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Graph search-based planners represent the continuous configuration space as nodes within a graph and search for feasible connections between these nodes to guide the vehicle toward its destination. Stahn et al. [15] generated and verified maneuvers around obstacles for a full-sized vehicle using A*. Xu et al. [16] proposed an improved A* algorithm for articulated robots, while [17] applied Dijkstra’s algorithm on a grid of pre-computed path segments. Similarly, [18] used a search method along with a steering function to reverse a general 2-trailer system. In [11] the authors proposed a hybrid A* along with jump point search to improve real-time performance. However, graph search-based methods are computationally demanding, especially in high-dimensional spaces.

Regarding optimization-based methods, authors in [19] applied an MPC algorithm for a truck and trailer system, while [20] proposed a trajectory planner for a car-like tractor with N trailers, based on an extension of hybrid A* to provide an initial guess for the optimization. Such methods calculate exact and optimal feasible paths, but remain computationally intensive, especially as the environment complexity increases.

Sampling-based algorithms, such as Rapidly-exploring Random Trees (RRTs) and Probabilistic Roadmaps (PRMs) are widely used to efficiently navigate complex environments. The PRM planner constructs a roadmap offline by sampling points in configuration space and connects nearby points with local planning [21], which is unsuitable for dynamic environments due to the need for a pre-built roadmap. Lattice-based path planner uses a finite set of pre-computed motion segments online. Lattice planning combined with optimal control for enhanced efficiency is described in [22] and [23] utilize lattice for a general two-trailer system. Nevertheless, such approaches do not utilize the full maneuvering capabilities of truck-trailer systems, while the robot’s actual position and orientation might not perfectly align with the lattice points, due to discretization.

RRT-based algorithms bypass the need for intricate configuration space modeling, while preserving high path-search efficiency in complex environments. Closed-loop RRT [24] samples an input to a stable closed-loop system, allowing a general two-trailer system to traverse the path with respect to the kinematic constraints. Authors in [25] incorporate heuristic rules within an RRT algorithm to deal with semi-trailer truck parking problem. Motion planning for a truck and trailer system is described in [8], which applies a randomized-kinodynamic approach for motion planning, while authors in [2] proposed a cascade framework that combines CL-RRT and Iterative Analytical Method (IAM) that enables bidirectional maneuverability for various truck-trailer parking scenarios. Palmieri et al. [26] developed Theta*-RRT algorithm for a truck-trailer system, where initially an any-angle path is derived from the vehicle to the target position and then a tree expands around the generated path using steering function to satisfy non-holonomic constraints.

RRT methods with kinematically-aware constraints have been recently proposed. In KB-RRT [27], the expansion of RRT is restricted to feasible regions of the state space opti-

mizing the path itself and improving the computation required to generate the path. Wang et al. [28] additionally performs branch pruning to optimize path length, while increasing computational efficiency and Ye et al. [10] proposed an APF approach to improve planning efficiency and performance. However, the above-mentioned works refer to unicycle robot kinematics.

Our work is based on a sampling-based planning method, in order to address challenges arised from complex environments, while maintaining the low computational complexity for plan generation. Specifically, our main contribution lies in the expansion of iKB-RRT [10] for a robot-trailer configuration, which facilitates complex maneuvering in challenging areas, respecting the non-linear robot kinematic constraints.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Kinematics

We consider an ackermann robot with trailer, with the following state vector:

$$X = [x, y, \theta, \alpha] \quad (1)$$

where x, y and θ are the position and the orientation of the robot respectively, and α is the trailer angle with respect to the robot’s longitudinal axis. The control vector of the system contains the linear velocity v and the steering angle γ :

$$U = [v, \gamma] \quad (2)$$

We approximate our system’s kinematics with the kinematic model, instead of the dynamic, since it remains accurate in low operating velocities. Adapting the formulation from [29]:

$$\dot{x} = v \cos(\theta) \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{y} = v \sin(\theta) \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \frac{v}{B} \tan(\gamma) \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{\alpha} = -\frac{v}{B} (\tan(\gamma) + \frac{B \sin(\alpha)}{L_t} + \frac{L_h \tan(\gamma) \cos(\alpha)}{L_t}) \quad (6)$$

where B is the baseline length of the robot, L_t is the length of the trailer and L_h is the hitch length.

B. APF-based KB-RRT

APF-based methods comprise of an attractive field to direct the robot towards the goal, and a repulsive field to push the robot away from obstacles. Our path planning algorithm builds upon iKB-RRT [10], a kinematically constrained, bi-directional RRT method guided by an APF. We extend this method by integrating knowledge of trailer kinematics to generate trajectories that consider the trailer angle, ensuring it remains within the permissible limits. The overall procedure is visualized in Fig. 1. The analysis of our approach begins with the RRT. Especially, each node of the RRT corresponds to a specific robot state, denoted as $X_i = [x_i, y_i, \theta_i, \alpha_i]$. Firstly, our algorithm initiates the start state, X_{start} , and the goal state, X_{goal} . KB-RRT expansion involves the development of

Fig. 1: Visualization of APF-based KB-RRT expansion for robot with trailer.

two trees: one extending forward from X_{start} and the other extending backward from X_{goal} . Iteratively, for each tree, a new node X_{sample} is created by uniformly sampling the robot's configuration space using a random generator function. Subsequently, the nearest node X_{near} to the newly generated node within the existing tree is identified by computing the euclidean distance.

An intermediate guiding step is implemented. This step leverages the APF, generated by obstacles near X_{near} , the sampled node X_{sample} , and X_{goal} to create an auxiliary node X_{guide} , which then becomes the target node in place of the random node X_{sample} . Specifically, the negative gradient of the APF generates the magnitudes of the forces that act upon the nearest node X_{near} from goal node (Eq. 7), sample node (Eq. 8) and obstacles (Eq. 9).

$$|\vec{F}_{goal}^{att}(X_{near})| = k_g \|X_{near} - X_{goal}\| \quad (7)$$

$$|\vec{F}_{sample}^{att}(X_{near})| = k_s \|X_{near} - X_{sample}\| \quad (8)$$

$$|\vec{F}_{o_i}^{rep}(X_{near})| = \begin{cases} k_o \left(\frac{1}{d_i} - \frac{1}{\rho_o} \right) \frac{1}{d_i^2}, & d_i \leq \rho_o \\ 0, & d_i > \rho_o \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where d_i denote the euclidean distance between node X_{near} and i -th obstacle. Parameter ρ_o is the obstacles range of action, and k_g, k_s are the weight coefficients for goal and sample node respectively. The total force \vec{F}_{total} acting on the nearest node is computed by aggregating all force vectors:

$$\vec{F}_{total} = \vec{F}_{sample}^{att} + \vec{F}_{goal}^{att} + \sum_{i=1}^M \vec{F}_{o_i}^{rep} \quad (10)$$

The guide node, X_{guide} is generated along the direction of the \vec{F}_{total} and its coordinates are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{guide_x} &= X_{near_x} + s \frac{F_x}{|\vec{F}_{total}|} \\ X_{guide_y} &= X_{near_y} + s \frac{F_y}{|\vec{F}_{total}|} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where F_x and F_y are the decomposed forces of \vec{F}_{total} along the X- and Y-axes of the global coordinate system, respectively, and s is the extension distance. Then, the ackermann and trailer kinematic model is employed to extend the tree from X_{near} towards X_{guide} . The generated configurations X_{new} account for the kinematics of the trailer, ensuring that the trailer angles remain within their physical bounds.

C. Backwards-tree numerical solution with Newton-Raphson

The KB-RRT framework tackles robot motion planning by considering the robot's physical limitations. In the forward growing tree, potential next positions are determined by sampling random velocities and feeding them through the robot's motion model. However, this approach cannot be transferred directly to the backward tree for complex systems, such as the ackermann robot with a trailer attached. Since Eq. 6 is non-linear and cannot be solved analytically, it is not feasible to solve the system of equations (3)-(6) backwards and obtain the robot's configuration at time $t - 1$ given the configuration at time t or reverse time using negative velocities. To address this, we employ the Newton-Raphson (NR) method, a numerical approach capable to iteratively calculate the valid trailer angle configuration for a previous time step. This ensures the backward tree expansion adheres to the robot's kinematic constraints, while generating a complete plan.

We use the backward finite difference approach to discretize the differential equations (3)-(6), in order to obtain an expression that connects the current configuration at time t_k , $X_k = [x_k, y_k, \theta_k, \alpha_k]$ with the previous one, $X_{k-1} = [x_{k-1}, y_{k-1}, \theta_{k-1}, \alpha_{k-1}]$:

$$X_k = f(X_{k-1}, U_{k-1}) \quad (12)$$

Eq. 12 is straightforward to solve for x_{k-1} , y_{k-1} and θ_{k-1} . However, for the trailer angle equation, we need to utilize NR method to solve for α_{k-1} and consequently obtain a feasible configuration X_{k-1} . Following the methodology described in [10], we sample control commands and provide them to the backward kinematic model, in order to obtain multiple X_{k-1} configurations and select the one which is closer to X_{guide} .

For the convergence of the NR method, we use a tolerance of 10^{-6} . This provides a balance between accuracy and computational time. A practical consideration regarding this approach is related to the cases where the computed trailer angle falls outside of the feasible region for a given sample control input. Specifically, this occurs when the target trailer angle is high and simultaneously the sampled velocities require the initial angle to be even higher to generate a feasible trajectory, leading to the computation of an angle which

exceeds the allowable bounds. In such cases, the sampled velocities are deemed invalid, and new velocities are sampled until a feasible solution is obtained.

Even though the solver was capable to compute a feasible configuration that allows the connection with the current one, the backward tree expansion became trapped in loops and did not expand further. This is caused due to the APF bias, which exerts a specific force at a given node when the tree attempts to expand from a specific node and the APF guides it towards a desired direction. Among the feasible candidates, the configuration that minimizes the cost (i.e. the distance from the guide node) is selected, leading the backwards growing tree to be stuck at a local minima. To this end, a relaxation to the influence of the APF is introduced. Specifically, a strategy which allowed the tree to expand randomly every few iterations is designed, thereby reducing the influence of the APF. This adjustment has proven effective in mitigating the observed phenomenon.

Regarding the connection of the two growing trees in bi-directional RRT approaches, the so-called merging problem, a simple distance criterion cannot be used in our case. Since kinematic feasibility is the required objective, a smooth connection between the two trees is necessary, similarly to [10]. However, in the case of robot-trailer configuration, the trailer angle must be taken into account during the merging phase.

To address this issue, we propose a set of heuristic evaluation metrics to determine whether the two trees can be merged. For two candidate nodes, $X_f = [x_f, y_f, \theta_f, \alpha_f]$ and $X_b = [x_b, y_b, \theta_b, \alpha_b]$, which correspond to forward and backward trees respectively, we denote the following criteria: $C1$ for the euclidean distance, $C2$ for the orientation difference, $C3$ for the relative angle difference and $C4$ for the trailer angle difference. Each criterion is expressed in Table I:

TABLE I: Tree merging criteria

Criterion	Expression
C1	$\sqrt{(x_f - x_b)^2 + (y_f - y_b)^2} < d_{max}$
C2	$ \theta_f - \theta_b < \theta_{max}$
C3	$ \text{atan2}[(x_f - x_b), (y_f - y_b)] - \theta_f < \theta_{r_{max}}$
C4	$ \alpha_f - \alpha_b < a_{max}$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

To validate the efficacy of our proposed method, we conducted experiments using a mobile robot with an articulated trailer in Gazebo simulator [30], as depicted in Fig. 2. The geometric characteristics of the mobile robot are $B = 1.0m$, $L_t = 1.0m$ and $L_h = 0.0m$, given that the hitch mount is located at the rear axle of the robot. The APF weight coefficients were set to $k_o = 4$, $k_t = 25$ for the goal node and $k_t = 50$ for the sample node. The thresholds for the tree merging were set to $d_{max} = 1.0m$, $\theta_{r_{max}} = 0.5rad$, $\theta_{max} = 0.4rad$, $a_{max} = 0.4rad$ and the obstacle range of action to $\rho_o = 6.0m$

We conducted quantitative comparison with the methodology proposed by Ye et al. [10], which is recognized for

its effectiveness in global planning within unstructured and complex environments. Our assessment focused on path length and the number of nodes required for computation to evaluate the efficiency of our path planning method. Additionally, we analyzed the mean curvature to demonstrate the impact of considering trailer kinematics in path planning.

Fig. 2: Robot with trailer in the simulation environment.

In Fig. 3 we present the results for both the baseline and our proposed planner. Notably, our method exhibits a slight increase in path length; however, the length remains comparable to those produced by the baseline. This increase is expected, as our planner generates trajectories with a larger turning radius to adhere to the kinematic constraints of the trailer, thereby necessitating a longer travel distance for the robot. In terms of mean path curvature, which is calculated using the Menger approach [31], our planner generates paths with reduced mean curvature, resulting in smoother trajectories and larger turning radius, which are key prerequisites for robust robot-trailer navigation. Concerning the computational time required for creating the path, our method requires a larger number of nodes. This is expected for two reasons. Firstly, due to the relaxation step applied to the backwards growing tree, there is greater randomness in its expansion. Consequently, it takes more random than educated steps towards the other tree, slightly delaying the algorithm's convergence. Secondly, the stricter criteria we employ for merging the two trees result in the rejection of nodes that the baseline method would accept as feasible merge points. Consequently, the number of iterations required for our algorithm is increased.

Given the initial conditions depicted in Fig. 4(a), the baseline global planner generates a path characterized by a small turning radius, leading to the folding of the trailer. Conversely, our method takes into account the limitations imposed by the trailer, producing a smoother path that adheres to the trailer's constraints. Fig. 4(c) illustrates the computed trailer angle, with colored points serving as references to align with corresponding positions along the trajectory. Additionally, Fig. 4(c) includes also the estimated trailer angle for the baseline method. As anticipated, the trailer angle in this case increases further, ultimately surpassing the kinematic limits. Consequently, only the initial time steps are depicted in the diagram. In the second scenario (S2), the robot begins with the trailer aligned with its orientation. As depicted in Fig. 4(b), our proposed approach generates a smoother trajectory towards

Fig. 3: Path length, number of nodes and mean curvature comparison between baseline planner and our proposed method.

Fig. 4: Qualitative results.

the final goal. In contrast, the baseline approach plans a trajectory that requires a sharp turn at the beginning of the path, causing the trailer angle to increase rapidly and reach the kinematic limit, as shown in Fig. 4(d). Furthermore, the baseline method necessitates another sharp turn near the end of the path. Due to the trailer angle surpassing its allowable limits, the corresponding diagram is terminated shortly after the trajectory starts. On the contrary, our method maintains the estimated trailer angle within the folding constraints, ensuring a feasible and smooth path.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a path planning method for a robot-trailer configuration is proposed. Our approach aims at planning efficient and collision-free global plans incorporating trailer kinematics in a large-scale and complex environment to accommodate precise and safe navigation. To this end, an APF-based KB-RRT approach was extended to facilitate non-linear kinematic constraints. Simulation results prove that our approach maintains increased path quality and computational cost, while

the planned trajectories respect robot-trailer kinematics and ensure safe navigation under various initial and final robot configurations. t

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. Balaska, K. Tsiakas, D. Giakoumis, I. Kostavelis, D. Folinias, A. Gasteratos, and D. Tzovaras, "A viewpoint on the challenges and solutions for driverless last-mile delivery," *Machines*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 1059, 2022.
- [2] A. C. Manav and I. Lazoglu, "A novel cascade path planning algorithm for autonomous truck-trailer parking," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 23, pp. 6821–6835, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:233703605>
- [3] J. J.-C. Lin, W.-H. Hung, and S.-C. Kang, "Motion planning and coordination for mobile construction machinery," *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, vol. 29, no. 6, p. 04014082, 2015.
- [4] K. Charalampous, I. Kostavelis, E. Boukas, A. Amanatiadis, L. Nalpanitidis, C. Emmanouilidis, and A. Gasteratos, "Autonomous robot path planning techniques using cellular automata," *Robots and lattice automata*, pp. 175–196, 2015.
- [5] T. Recker, M. Matour, and A. Raatz, "A simple and modular approach to path planning for tractor-trailer robots based on modification of pre-existing trajectories," in *Proceedings of the Conference on Production Systems and Logistics : CPSL 2021*, D. Herberger and M. Hübner, Eds., vol. 5. Hannover: publish-Ing., 2021, pp. 136–145.
- [6] M. Yue, X. Hou, X. Zhao, and X. Wu, "Robust tube-based model predictive control for lane change maneuver of tractor-trailer vehicles based on a polynomial trajectory," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 5180–5188, 2020.
- [7] Z. Duraklı and V. Nابیev, "A new approach based on bezier curves to solve path planning problems for mobile robots," *Journal of Computational Science*, vol. 58, p. 101540, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187750321001988>
- [8] P. Zips, M. Böck, and A. Kugi, "An optimisation-based path planner for truck-trailer systems with driving direction changes," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Robotics and Automation*, Seattle, WA, USA, May 2015, pp. 630–636.
- [9] K. Charalampous, I. Kostavelis, and A. Gasteratos, "Thorough robot navigation based on svm local planning," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 70, pp. 166–180, 2015.

- [10] L. Ye, F. Wu, X. Zou, and J. Li, "Path planning for mobile robots in unstructured orchard environments: An improved kinematically constrained bi-directional rrt approach," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 215, p. 108453, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168169923008414>
- [11] D. Li, L. Gao, B. Jia, Y. Yang, M. Fu, and S. Xie, "An environmental and behavioral-oriented search-based trajectory planning approach for tractor-trailer system in narrow environment," in *2023 IEEE 26th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 2023, pp. 3825–3830.
- [12] L. Ma, J. Xue, K. Kawabata, J. Zhu, C. Ma, and N. Zheng, "Efficient sampling-based motion planning for on-road autonomous driving," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 1961–1976, 2015.
- [13] X. Ruan, Y. Huang, Y. Wang, Z. Fu, L. Xiong, and Z. Yu, "An efficient trajectory-planning method with a reconfigurable model for any tractor-trailer vehicle," *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3360–3374, 2023.
- [14] X. Zhang, J. Eck, and F. Lotz, "A path planning approach for tractor-trailer system based on semi-supervised learning," in *2022 IEEE 25th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 2022, pp. 3549–3555.
- [15] R. Stahn, T. Stark, and A. Stopp, "Laser scanner-based navigation and motion planning for truck-trailer combinations," in *2007 IEEE/ASME international conference on advanced intelligent mechatronics*. IEEE, 2007, pp. 1–6.
- [16] Y. Xu and R. Liu, "Path planning for mobile articulated robots based on the improved a* algorithm," *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 1729881417728013, 2017.
- [17] A. J. Rimmer and D. Cebon, "Planning collision-free trajectories for reversing multiply-articulated vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 1998–2007, 2016.
- [18] P. Töws and D. Zöbel, "Reversing general 2-trailer vehicles using a 2d steering function model and a novel mesh search algorithm," in *2021 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1274–1281.
- [19] M. Bos, B. Vandewal, W. Decré, and J. Swevers, "Mpc-based motion planning for autonomous truck-trailer maneuvering," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 4877–4882, 2023, 22nd IFAC World Congress. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405896323016622>
- [20] B. Li, T. Acarman, Y. Zhang, L. Zhang, C. Yaman, and Q. Kong, "Tractor-trailer vehicle trajectory planning in narrow environments with a progressively constrained optimal control approach," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, vol. 5, pp. 414–425, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:212808315>
- [21] Q. Han, Y. Huang, J. Yuan, and Y. Kang, "A method of path planning for tractor-trailer mobile robot based on the concept of global-width," in *Fifth World Congress on Intelligent Control and Automation (IEEE Cat. No. 04EX788)*, vol. 6. IEEE, 2004, pp. 4773–4777.
- [22] K. Bergman, O. Ljungqvist, and D. Axehill, "Improved path planning by tightly combining lattice-based path planning and optimal control," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 57–66, 2020.
- [23] O. Ljungqvist, N. Evestedt, M. Cirillo, D. Axehill, and O. Holmer, "Lattice-based motion planning for a general 2-trailer system," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1703.03616>
- [24] N. Evestedt, O. Ljungqvist, and D. Axehill, "Motion planning for a reversing general 2-trailer configuration using closed-loop rrt," in *2016 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2016, pp. 3690–3697.
- [25] R. Lattarulo, J. Pérez, and J. Murgoitio, "Rrt trajectory planning approach for automated semi-trailer truck parking," in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Vehicular Electronics and Safety (ICVES)*, 2022, pp. 1–7.
- [26] L. Palmieri, S. Koenig, and K. O. Arras, "Rrt-based nonholonomic motion planning using any-angle path biasing," *2016 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 2775–2781, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:17830026>
- [27] D. Ghosh, G. Nandakumar, K. Narayanan, V. Honkote, and S. Sharma, "Kinematic constraints based bi-directional rrt (kb-rrt) with parameterized trajectories for robot path planning in cluttered environment," in *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2019, pp. 8627–8633.
- [28] J. Wang, B. Li, and M. Q.-H. Meng, "Kinematic constrained bi-directional rrt with efficient branch pruning for robot path planning," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 170, p. 114541, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0957417420311854>
- [29] M. Werling, P. Reinisch, M. Heidingsfeld, and K. Gresser, "Reversing the general one-trailer system: Asymptotic curvature stabilization and path tracking," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 627–636, 2014.
- [30] N. Koenig and A. Howard, "Design and use paradigms for gazebo, an open-source multi-robot simulator," in *2004 IEEE/RSJ international conference on intelligent robots and systems (IROS)(IEEE Cat. No. 04CH37566)*, vol. 3. IEEE, 2004, pp. 2149–2154.
- [31] J. C. Léger, "Menger curvature and rectifiability," 1999. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/math/9905212>